

**COUNTER TERRORISM IN THE NIGER DELTA AND THE
DRAMATIST'S SOCIAL VISION: A CRITICAL READING OF AHMED
YERIMA'S *HARD GROUND***

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Abstract

Insurgency in the oil-rich Niger Delta region of Nigeria, which threatens the peace of the masses and the activities of multinational corporations, and endangers the nation's economy is terrorism. The persistent situation, which cannot be wished away, is a challenge that calls for urgent redress. Ahmed Yerima's social vision in *Hard Ground* (2006) is a commitment towards positive change in the issues of terrorism in the Niger Delta region. This study aims to undertake textual content analysis of *Hard Ground* to examine the dramatist's prescription for counterterrorism in the Niger Delta, while evaluating the present security measures deployed to combat terrorism in the region. The study anchors on Stakeholder Theory, which insists on the ethical obligation of corporations to stakeholders who may be affecting corporate activities. The paper submits that the corporate activities on the natural resources of the Niger Delta region are exploitative; endangering the region, and the insurgency is therefore a secular agitation, which can be nipped in the bud through dialogue in fairness, rather than combat and war. This paper recommends that Government and the multinational corporations should evaluate the danger of exploitations in the region and dialogue with all stakeholders for a framework for ethical obligation, which is fair and acceptable by all parties in the interest of peace in the region and the stability of the nation's economy.

Keywords:

Dramatist Social Vision, Insurgency, Counterterrorism, Ethical obligation, Niger Delta Region

Introduction

There is a thin line between freedom fighting and Terrorism. Schmid describes Terrorism:

As a method of combat in which random or symbolic victims become targets of violence. Through the repeated use of violence or the credible threat of violence, members of a society or another group are put into fear (terror) ... the purpose of Terrorism is either to immobilize the target of terror in order to produce disorientation and/or compliance, or to mobilize secondary targets of attention (111).

The above description explains terrorism as a threat against man's peace, existence and development. The menace of terrorism and its consequence as it affects a nation state has been in existence long before now and terrorism in Nigeria has attracted global attention. Scholars observe that the acts of Terrorism have been hampering the development of the Nigerian society. Abugh [17], Ogologoma [3], Akasike & Adelekan, [201]. Eke observes that:

Recent events in Nigeria have indicated an emerging trend in the form of terrorism. It would be recalled that in Sept. 12, 2007, the Australian government issued a warning for its citizens to re-consider their needs in travelling to Nigeria, due to the high threat of terrorist attack, kidnapping and civil unrest. This was sequel to an earlier warning issued on Sept. 6, 2007 by the US Mission in Lagos to her citizens against travelling to Nigeria due to same reason. As of then, the terrorist activities in the Niger Delta; hostage taking, kidnapping and other criminal activities was just taking shape (1).

Terrorism in Nigeria is not restricted to the series of uprising in the northern part of Nigeria that is usually fueled by religious doctrines, but also the crises in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. Ogologoma rightly observes that:

The situation in the oil rich Niger Delta region necessitates a special attention for concern not only because of the level of environmental degradation there, but because of the rate and dimensions of militancy and militarization. At the heart of the conflict lies the question of who should exercise control over the oil explored and exploited from the oil rich region (2).

Abugh also adds that "Exploitation has awakened the people to fight for their rights vide militarization. Fueled by the hanging of Ken Saro Wiwa and other

eight Ogoni activists in 1995 by the military regime of Gen Sani Abacha, the oil crises have led to the emergence of militant groups from the region” (180). Indigenes have formed themselves into militia groups such as; Movement for the survival of Ogoni people (MOSSOP), Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), Niger Delta People Volunteer Front (NDPVF), Joint Revolution Council and Avengers, to mention a few. These groups have a unified goal of staging virulent, radical and ravaging protests against exploitation, reckless exploration, socio-economic terrorism, and unfavourable government policies that administer the multinational oil company’s operation.

Idorenyin and Matthew assert that:

The people of the Niger Delta are socio-economically neglected, they don’t benefit from the oil proceeds, considering the fact that oil is extracted from their region. Instead, the people’s original sources of livelihood have been paralyzed due to environmental degradation caused by the activities of oil exploration (4).

It is in this regard that this paper examines the issue of terrorism in the Niger Delta as captured in Ahmed Yerima’s *Hard Ground* to exteriorize the counter-terrorism measures that could be invaluable for the contemporary Nigerian Society.

Niger Delta Crisis and Terrorism

The Niger Delta comprises states in Nigeria that are bordered by coastal waters of the Atlantic. The Niger Delta is a wetland characterized by rivers, rivulets, streams, canals and creeks that are rich in crude oil. Anyaegbunam adds that “the Niger Delta lies within some twenty-two major estuaries that are linked locally to a complicated network of mangrove creeks, rich in Wetlands, biodiversity, oil and gas, as well as human resources” (20). The above description presents the Niger Delta as a place that is rich in mineral deposits and biodiversity, which should naturally complement the aboriginal preoccupation in fishing and agrarian culture.

Upon the discovery of Oil in 1956 at Oloibiri, government had engaged multinational companies without a medium-, short- or long-term plan for the development of the place; they rushed into reckless exploration leading to degradation, pollution of the environment, health and environmental hazards. This consciousness incites the people to resort to violent conflicts and militancy. Ibaba states that:

The Niger Delta crisis is caused by the following factors: Land alienation, unfulfilled promises for compensation, political

marginalization, socio-economic inequalities, dishonest leadership, communication gap, inadequate research input and cultural disorientation (qtd in Idorenyin and Matthew, 3)

The above submission reveals the primary causes of terrorism in the region. Prior to the oil exploitation, the Niger Delta people had been engaging in palm oil production and other agricultural proceeds, but upon oil exploration, their preoccupation was lost. Consequently, fishes move away from contaminated water, continuous gas flaring affects the growth and productivity of crops, thus, their farmlands were lost to oil exploration. Olawari also writes on the causal factor of Terrorism and Counter Terrorism in the Niger Delta:

There is a political, physical, economic and social threat to agriculture in the region. Aside food security, agriculture is a catalyst for peace as it guarantees a stable income. However, since the inception of oil exploration, the people have lost their sources of livelihood as their lands are contaminated (qtd in Odoemene, 124).

This submission infers that, the Niger Delta people are politically marginalized, because they are part of the ethnic minority, they also feel helpless when their chances for survival are taken forcibly away from them. So, this frustration propels them to resort to militarization. Arikpo argues that “the communities of the Niger Delta from whose land oil is produced are excluded from oil wealth, the people of the Niger Delta believe that they have no substantial benefit to show for their sacrifices, despite being ‘the goose’ that laid the golden egg” (qtd Ephraim, 7)

However, security agents have, in a bid to respond to the militant-terrorist activities in the region, brutalized the agitators and their kindred. Ephraim attests that “many of the locals have been maimed, women raped and many have met untimely deaths. Local villages like Odi, Opia-Ikenyan, Okerenkoko and Ogoni-land have been destroyed by the Nigerian military through the use of excessive force in counter insurgency measures” (7). The rising agitation by the people draw national and international attentions to these social, political, economic and environmental injustices being perpetrated in the region. Maduboko submits that:

The People of the Niger Delta have endured more than six decades and two years of the suspension from the proceeds of their land. It is monstrous injustice which has been visited upon them by groups who concede behind the nationalities and states of the Federation to communalize the property of the minorities. We must all remember that whether it is a subversion of people's will or the

appropriation of their resources, injustice in any form and perspective breeds anarchy (Vanguard, Tuesday, May 1, p. 24, 2007).

Maduboko also adds that different revolutionary groups emerged and began to challenge governmental forces/agents, sent to protect oil facilities over the ownership and control of oil resources in the region; “their activities included kidnapping of oil workers for ransom, blowing up oil-pipelines, crude oil bunkering and stealing, including general disruption of oil exploration activities in the Niger Delta” - all geared at drawing government’s attention to the plights of the people.

Terrorism and Counter Terrorism

Terrorism is necessitated by conflict. Conflict is the occurrence of a clash or disagreement between people, organizations or groups contending for motives. Terrorism is the unlawful use of violence against persons or groups to intimidate or coerce a government or individual for personal, political, or social interest.

In this article, terrorism is perceived as all acts of physical and psychological conflicts propelled by panic or fear, intimidation, use of extreme force, revenge, destruction, coercion, threats of violence or vandalism, on persons or group of persons, organizations, corporation, or the general public with the intention of pressurizing a government, body, individuals, institution or organization or to forcibly act in ways contrary to societal norms. Oftentimes, the actions are claimed to be ways to ensure safety of lives and property, rights advocacy, defense, ethnic considerations, equity, justice or fairness; especially from the point of view of the perpetrators of the terror. On the other hand, counter-terrorism in this context describes all forms of organized reactive measures, techniques, approaches and methods employed by persons, group or corporate bodies to surmount terrorism.

Social Vision of Dramatists

Every dramatist has a social vision. Dramatists are playwrights who deploy the dynamism of literature to project the historical antecedents of the people thereby unveiling the social, economic and political ills of the society. They owe a responsibility of commitment to social order and development. Abimbola Shittu states that:

The main concern of a socially committed dramatist is to see a change in the structure of the society and an eradication of the social ills that plague the society. He therefore works relentlessly to ensure that these problems are seen in their right perspectives,

apprehended totally and presented to the public as the bane of the society (122).

This justifies the fact that every artist is saddled with the responsibility of influencing the society he/she finds himself, improving the living conditions of people and bringing hope to hopeless situations. The committed writer pokes and points ways out of the mire to promote human dignity and pride. Within the framework of this study, the social vision of dramatists is used to mean the role of dramatists in pointing to the problems of the society thereby inciting concerned relevant authorities to take swift response towards alleviating them.

Theoretical Framework

This study hinges on Stakeholder theory (Freeman 233) which addresses morals and values in managing an organization and the interaction with external stakeholders. The theory models and identifies the groups which are stakeholders of a corporation and thus, device and recommends methods by which management can give due regard to the interest of the external groups. Freeman defines a stakeholder as “any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organization’s objectives” (233).

Harrison, Bosse and Phillips opine that, “A firm allocates more resources to satisfying the needs and demands of its legitimate stakeholders than what is necessary to simply retain their willful participation in the productive activities of the firm” (237). They further explain that while the human resource theory focuses on employees, marketing theory focuses on customers, financial theory focuses on shareholders and financiers, etc; likewise, stakeholder theory pays attention to the stakeholders and their core concerns to partnership (Parmar, Freeman, Harrison, Wicks, 238).

This Theory is apt for this study because the shareholders (Multinational companies exploring oil in the Niger Delta and governmental bodies) neglect the living conditions of the Niger Deltans (Stakeholders) that bear the consequences of reckless exploration and exploitation of resources in the Niger Delta thereby leading to murder for money. This theory thus advocates the inclusion of stakeholders’ interest in the exploration of the natural resource derived from the Niger Delta region to achieve lasting peace and dissuade recurrent insurgence & acts of terrorism. This is a veritable counter terrorism strategy for the Niger Delta region.

About the Drama *Hard Ground* (2013)

Synopsis

Nimi, the tragic hero of the play drops out of school because he wants to be a child soldier fighting for the rights of his people. This act brings out the bestial nature of man as the child engages in violence and different forms of terrorism. However, as he picks up ammunition, things grow from bad to worse for him and consequently, the Don is after his life as he is accused of masterminding the death of Don's boys. He is however released after his mother, Mama pays the ransom for his life. On getting home, he is advised not to go back to the creeks as Don is after his life. He however longs to see Pikibo, his pregnant wife. Towards the end of the play, Pikibo is killed and the child beheaded because it is discovered that she has been leaking the secrets of the boys, Nimi avenges her as he kills the Don in connivance with his mother when on a particular occasion, Don visits him. The play ends on a tragic note as Nimi, after killing the Don switches on the light to unveil the motionless body of the Don that happens to be Baba, his father.

Thematic Thrust

Ahmed Yerima's *Hard Ground* raises a lot of salient issues on oil exploitation and the militant's aggressiveness to revolt through terrorism and the government's approach of counter terrorism; one of such issues comes to bear when the playwright vehemently criticizes terrorism as a factor that ravages the entire society by killing of innocent people. This is a communal tragedy. **Baba;** you say nothing, twenty people died in the camp, butchered like sacrificial dogs... (10). The playwright also opposes the notion of fighting with ammunition by terrorist groups as more and more souls are extinguished from the society. This omen signifies a weak future for the natives, especially as nameless, well-to-do politicians take advantage of the crises to prosper, do illegal ammunition business, demand a fair share of government funds, sponsor and incite the terrorists to perpetrate violence.

Mama...I have already lost a brother. Ten years ago, his blood is still splashed on the doorway of my family house when he was killed trying to run into our family compound. He was butchered like a dog by the same men who played with him as a child and fed with him as a man... (15).

Yerima creatively informs the society that terrorism is a self-destruct agent, it gives hope at first, everything falls into place but when the chips are down, it takes away the hope and use one's life as substitute. **Inyigifaa:** Yes, his cousins rescued you, now they want your life as a replacement... (21).

The playwright also reprehends Terrorism as he presents disunity, mishap, mistrust and mischief in the heart of chiefs of ethnic groups who killed one another, betrayed one another, leaked secrets to enemies and use the terrorism act as a cover up to amass wealth, power, fame and affluence to themselves, in the process, spilling the blood of one another.

Inyingifaa: The chiefs could not be trusted, and too much money was passing from hand to hand and nothing was being achieved. There was no trust anywhere, the air of mistrust was choking and the toll of dead bodies was mounting... The stream of blood was beginning to mix with the oily black soil. This was sad, even the police could not believe their luck, we were supposed to have one common enemy, not fight one another (22).

Mama: That animal killed my brother... now he wants to kill my son? What did I do to him and why does he want to destroy my family?

Nimi: Then I shall ask uncle Inyingifaa.

Mama: That one is a traitor. He will sell his own blood if the price is good, he measures everything in terms of money... (31).

Yerima also reflects how the Niger Deltans perpetrate terrorism vide pipeline vandalism, kidnapping, among others and points to the fact that they take pride in hampering development in their approach to opposition of multinational oppression. Another salient issue brought to limelight is the issue of Domestic Terrorism. The playwright reflects how women are beaten and maimed in their stead, robbed of any right to speak or live peacefully. **Mama:** ... Wife beater, come, beat me! I have nothing to lose now... (44).

Yerima bemoans Terrorism as it vitiates not only human existence but also envelops the catastrophe of a people's cultural and religious institutions thereby desecrating the consecrated, celebrated and elevated values of a people. For instance, Tingolongo informs the audience that Nimi and his men pursued their kinsmen because a fellow man ordered their death, the kinsmen seek protection by running into the shrine, but Nimi still killed and ordered a stick to be pushed through his anus and burnt right there in the shrine... (45). One implication of this desecration is the fact that the society is faced with wrath of the gods because the monuments and altars represent cultural ethos, it is believed that the forces will turn their backs on the people. **Tingolongo:** The way you killed him even offended the gods... (46).

The playwright however blames the government and other stakeholders as the cause of these dastardly acts, they inflict pains via exploitation of their resources, extinction of their pre occupation, dearth of drinkable water, contaminated farmlands, without adequate compensation, leaving them worse off, not only that, they also dehumanized and mock their existence by using them as errand boys, forgetting that a tool/instrument could someday be a weapon when twisted... it raises concern as this issue of terrorism is taking another new dimension; if not surmounted, it could lead to secession. **Nimi:** Oh my blood boils, I long for the swell of swamp. Breaking up this country is our next agenda... (37).

Yerima also exposes another main cause of terrorism as he blames the chiefs, business moguls, politicians who are paranoid with ambition and in their complexities of ignorance raised a small fire that razed their entire household to ruins. They embarked on desperate bid to enrich themselves by giving the boys guns and money to vandalize pipeline so they could be 'settled'. These boys soon became men and revolted against their lords.

Nimi: They created us. They gave us a reason to find our place... first we were errand boys, and so we got guns and money. We started to ask questions, they had no answers. They all knew what they looked like before they got into power. We dumped them. They gave us no respect because of the crumbs they give us while they keep the chunk... (37).

Apart from the radical desire to question the status quo, Yerima is psychologically pissed that one man eats to his fill while another who owns the food is emaciated, impoverished and malnourished. Yerima draws the attention of the government and stakeholders alike to the obsolete and inefficient radical fire-for-fire approach of combatting terrorism as no significant result has been recorded. The soldiers pursue the terrorist groups and lay ambush to slaughter them.

Nimi: I did not kill them. There was a parrot in our midst, our every move had been given away. After Capon had been shot in the exchange that we had with canoe boys, I took over before Danger Arrow could send us a new Capon. I organized the breaking up of some pipes so no one was supposed to know except me and the boys but the soldiers were there waiting. All my eighteen boys were killed... (pp 12-14).

The playwright further raises a concern over the efficacy of this measure as this approach of combatting terrorism hasn't helped the Nigerian government so far, as the terrorist groups recruit more personnel on almost daily basis. **Nimi:** why

does mama cry? There are younger boys and girls than me in the struggle...” (pp. 11-12). This connotes the fact that terrorism is in every household, nook and crannies of our stead and sooner or later if something isn't done, it would drift us to perdition. The terrorists care little about death and from gradual nightmares of seeing blood after every kill, they become hard-hearted expert terrorists who see death of a fellow man as social norm.

Nimi: ... even when in primary school, you live in pain and then it sounds right to join the struggle, first as a boy of a group, then as the eye or a spy. By the time you are halfway through primary school, you carry guns for the boys and by the time you are eleven, in these days of automatic guns, you become an expert. You see, people die every day, either of hunger or just death so it means nothing to you. It is a hard life, mama.

Mama: and you can sleep son?

Nimi: with nightmares at first, the foam of the blood of your dead foes making you sweat at first in the nose, then mouth, and then your neck even on cold harmattan nights, then soundly as the faces of the dead people multiply, and killing means nothing to you anymore, soundly your eyelids shut to the cries of the world and you justify in your heart that the people you killed are the enemies of the land, not yours as an individual, and after a while, all you think about are the fiery songs of the people, and the good of the land and then you sleep like a new born each time you catch a wink... (12).

The playwright however condemns the approaches used to make demands for the struggle as danger looms with each soul terrorized by death on daily basis, for a cause that is not for the interest of the people. This according to him portends a bleak future, as little children, young and old are hacked to death by circumstances of one man's avarice, the terrorists feel the forces of existence are in their support at each step not knowing even the forces are tired of seeing deaths of people who ought to worship and offer unto them sacrifices to keep the tripartite worldview intact.

Tingolongo: That is all I take from here these days, young souls, old souls, maimed souls, little boys and girls whose destinies are still hanging, forcefully dragged to me. Some headless, some faceless, some eaten up by fishes and periwinkles, oh man, you are wicked! The gods are angry... (47).

Tingolongo: (*chuckles*) the people have to die. For whose cause? (*Chuckles again*) yours or theirs? (*Strong voice*) The gods need the people! When you kill them all, who will worship us? Who will pour libation at the shrines? Who will sing our praises hum? You have become a disease which robs the children of the swampy fields of their future, instead of giving them life. Childish fool! (48).

The question of counter terrorism in the play is also revisited by the playwright as he questions who terrorizes who and why is a force of terrorism contending with another? Yerima reveals that the forces of rival-indigenes (Militant-Terrorists), Chiefs, Government, Soldiers do not combat terror in the interest of the populace but for their personal interest. For instance, Inyigifaa told Nimi's mother how he rescued him for safety whereas he seeks vengeance that his business had collapsed and other paranoid politicians have overtaken him owing to Nimi's fault:

Inyigifaa: My business stopped. My shipment could not pass through. No one wanted my guns. I was told that the big men had established another route and another source. My men were killed, paraded on television that they were caught bunkering. But I never meddle in oil, only guns. Now, the lives of my boys must be avenged. (*He brings out a dagger, and moves towards Nimi, determined to hurt him*)... (22).

Yerima also raises a question of who gave the Terrorists power over death. Terrorism is a cankerworm that kills not only the victims but leaves an everlasting imprint of tragedy on the perpetrators and this justifies Pikibo (Nimi's pregnant fiance) and the Don's (Nimi's father) painful death, the former was hung by the neck with a string of wire and her skin sliced piece by piece, the unborn child ripped out of her womb and beheaded, innocent as the baby was. This act infuriated Nimi but he keeps his cool as he nursed the ambition of killing him someday. The day the Don was visiting, Nimi connived with his mother (Mama) to murder him as vengeance unknown to him, the Don visiting, is his father... **Nimi:** I have killed the devil, did you not hear how the bastard fell on the ground? I slit his throat with one stroke... (*Nimi turns the body, slowly, he removes the scarf*)... Mama, it is Baba... (59).

The playwright, also condemns the use of terror to counter terror in the region as it leaves the environmental, socio-economical, ecological and human capital development devastated beyond repair, to Yerima, Justice, fairness and equity is

a key determinant in achieving long lasting peace in any violence disturbed nation-state.

Nimi; It hits him bad. "Show me a perfect community", he screamed, losing his cool. "We cannot use arms to fight arms", he screeched with the sound of the cheap microphone. "Lasting peace could only be achieved when there is justice" (36).

Yerima further condemns the use of terror in the region by natives to make known their demand as lives on daily basis are put to jeopardy and displaces the terrorist act as a factor that not only kills an individual, but drifts the society to commit communal tragedy. Having explicated the causal agent of terrorism and the inability of multinational powers, stakeholders and government alike to curb its excesses so far, the playwright took exception to the use of terrorism to combat terror and consequently, recommends dialogism and an all-inclusive representation of the peasants (the ordinary citizens) in allocation and distribution of wealth. **Nimi:** He has promised to get me. But the good thing is that the president believes in talking with our warlords. They may achieve peace... (36). This conforms to Uwasomba' perspective that "the bourgeois of Yerima makes him place much premium on the high and mighty, than on the ordinary people, who are supposed to be the most important elements in the society" (qtd in Abugh, 185).

Alabo: Have we not leant anything? We must go beyond blood, blood, blood...you cannot always wait to be wasted, how many more great men, men of vision are we to lose? Death is not working. The world does not listen to young men in head bands, with AK47 guns, in the swamp. They will call them terrorists, guerilla fighters and both words mean killers, not heroes to them (38).

Although, *Hard Ground* can be regarded as a tragic play, it also reflects the love of women for their household, as Mama, owing to the fact that she doesn't want Nimi, her child to know she has a disease, sent him to the village which later dovetailed to his tragic fate.

Yerima analyses the issues bedevilling the Niger Delta society and advocates that unless a dialogue between warring factions is held, the society will drift to perdition, men will violate natural laws and become extremist in their search for wealth and fame while the ordinary people kill their relatives in ignorance. As rightly observed by Adeoye, in an Interview with Ahmed Yerima;

Like *Hard Ground*, I said this problem we are having in the Niger-Delta is going to eat us all up, it is going to get to a point where children are going to kill fathers, parents. Adults looking for positions and things and it is the wrong ones, negative ones they are looking for: Capone, foreign titles. This is going to destroy us if we do not curtail them, it is beautiful now but if we are not careful this thing will go out of the cubic and become a nightmare and that is what it is becoming and I can see things like that... (222).

This play has lucidly elaborated terrorism by revealing that the Niger Delta is under socio-economic, political and environmental “terrorism” of the Federal Government of Nigeria, multinational oil companies, and avarice, paranoid wealth seeking indigenes of the Niger Delta. It has in another vein outlined the modes and approaches various groups and individuals had undertaken to counter it and how such systems had merely added salt to injury rather than alleviate it. However, issues of ethnicity and marginalization also complement the crux of the matter.

Discussion

The playwright, through *Hard Ground*, has registered his protest against environmental, biological and aqua terrorism of the Niger Delta and its inhabitants. The Niger Deltans were rich in agriculture and aquaculture; fish farming, palm oil production, timber and crops to mention a few, before the discovery of crude oil, and since its discovery at Oloibiri, the shareholders (Government and Multinationals) didn't make any short or long term plan/policy for development of these people before the commencement of oil exploration and coupled with the loss of their aboriginal preoccupation; they feel justified to take adopt militarization as the only language to force the oppressors to listen.

The multinationals on the other hand deployed troops to curb the menace but this so far, has not put a lasting solution to the problem. The playwright observes this trend and calls for a review of such strategy, as it has only led to loss of lives, home, infrastructure and hampered development. Yerima opines that these militias have not effectively solved their problems but have only succeeded in inciting government to counter their terrorism with armed military insurrection. This would be the tide for a long time unless a consensus is reached through a discourse driven mentality that embraces an all-inclusive representation, women and youth empowerment, sincerity of purpose and improved living conditions.

Conclusion

It is pertinent to note that the federal government have taken different reactive steps to solve the problem, but so far, the issues of terrorism has been reduced but not totally eradicated, as such, a discourse driven mentality as an alternative to resolving this terrorism is one of the efficient strategies being proposed to curb this menace. As a committed dramatist, the playwright has demonstrated his clout as an intellectual voice and conscience of the society that informs the society about a situation. He considers his scholarship status as a medium for social change.

Hard Ground is one of the playwright's most passionate and profound protests against human, environmental and cultural terrorism. It is a voice berating violence against women and children, poverty, and socio-political exploitation. It also tells the society that where terrorism is used to counter terrorism, self-destruction of farmlands, homes and loved ones is inevitable, especially as government employs various military forces as Joint Task Force (JTF) to suppress the activities of these groups. Hence, religious, ethnic, socio cultural and tribal sentiments must be discouraged and rather, a rapid step inclined towards dialogism, youth and women empowerment, all-inclusive representation, patience, good governance and sincerity should be encouraged to permanently resolve the crisis.

Works Cited

- Abugh, Ben. "Little drops; Drama, Oil and Unrest in the Nigerian Niger Delta Region". *Journal of Theatre and Media Studies*, Vol 2, No. 1, 2017, Pp 179-189.
- Adeoye, Julius. "The Drama of Ahmed Yerima; Studies in Nigerian Theatre" Universiteit Leiden, 8th May, 2013, www.hdl.handle.net/1887/20858.
- Amaraegbu, Declan. "Violence, Terrorism and Security Threat in Nigeria's Niger Delta: An Old Problem taking a New Dimension" *African Journal of Political Science and International Relations*, Vol. 5, No. 4, 2011, Pp. 208-217.
- Amaraegbu, D. "Analysis of Anti-Corruption Policies in Africa: The Cases of Nigeria and Ghana". Berlin, VDM Publishing House, 2010. Pp 208-217.
- Anayaegbunam, A. O. "Niger Delta. A Case for Regional Contingency Plan". In Osuntokun (ed). *Environmental Problems of the Niger Delta*. Lagos: Friedrich Ebert Foundation. 2000.

- Arikpo, M. "Communal Conflicts in the East-Niger Delta: A Cultural Matrix". *Pan-African Social Science Review*. No. 3. 1998. Pp 37- 44.
- Boro, Isaac. "The Twelve-Day Revolution". Benin; Idodo Umeh Publishers, 1982. Print.
- Eke, Chijioke. "Terrorism and the Dilemmas of Combatting the Menace in Nigeria" *International Journal of Humanities*, Vol 3, No. 4, 2013, Pp 265-272.
- Eke, E. "Ethnic Militias and Criminality in Niger Delta" *African Research, Review: An International Multi-Disciplinary Journal*. Ethiopia: Vol.33. No 6, 2009, Pp 315-330.
- Essien, Ephraim. "Philosophy of Peace and Conflict beyond the United Nations". Calabar: University of Calabar Press, 2008. Print.
- Freeman, R.E "Response: Divergent Stakeholder Theory", *Academy of Management Review*, Vol 24, No. 2, 1999. Pp 233-236.
- Folarin, S. "Niger Delta: Environment, Ogoni Crisis and the State". *The Constitution: Journal of Constitutional Development*, Vol. 7, No. 1, 2007, Pp. 37-61.
- Harrison, J.S., Bosse, D.A. and Phillips, R.A. "Managing for Stakeholders, Stakeholder Utility Functions and Competitive Advantage". *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol 8, No. 31, 2010. Pp 58-74.
- Ibaba, S. I. "Understanding the Niger Delta Crisis". Port Harcourt: Amethyst and Colleagues Publishers. 2005. Print
- Idorenyin, Francis & Matthew Akpan. "The Niger Delta Crisis in Nigeria: Some Moral lessons" *International Journal of History and Philosophical Research*, Vol. 1, No. 1, 2013, Pp 1- 13.
- Ikechukwu, Dialoke & Marshall, Edeja. "Effects of Niger Delta Militancy on the Economic Development of Nigeria 2006-2016" *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Research*, Vol. 3, No.3, 2017, Pp 25-36.
- Lawal, Adeshina. "Violence in the Niger Delta". Osun Publishers, 2011. Print.
- Mabudoko, Christian. "Environmental Pollution: The Rise of Militarism and Terrorism in the Niger Delta of Nigeria". In *International Journal of Rural Law and Policy*, Vol. 1, No 4, 2014, Pp 1-13.
- Ogoloma, F. I. "Secularism in Nigeria: An Assessment". www.afrevjo.net.

- Ogoloma, Fineface. "Niger Delta Militants and the Boko Haram: A Comparative Appraisal" *AFRREV IJAH- An International Journal of Arts and Humanities*, Bahir Dar, Ethiopia Vol.2 No. 1, 2013, Pp 114-131.
- Phillips, R.A., Freeman, R.E. and Wicks, A.C. "What Stakeholder Theory is Not". *Business Ethics Quarterly*, Vol 13, 2003. Pp 479-502.
- Tamuno, T. "Oil Wars in the Niger Delta 1849-2009". Ibadan: Stirling-Horden Publishers Ltd, 2011, Pp 199. Print.
- Uwasamba, Chijioko. "Ideology, Politics and Powers in the Silent Gods". In Adeofi (ed) *Muse and Mimesis*: Ibadan; Spectrum Books Limited, 2007. Pp 68-78. Print
- Wicks, A.C. and Freeman, R.E. "Organization Studies and the New Pragmatism: Positivism, Anti- Positivism, and the search for Ethics. *Organization Science*, Vol 9. No 8, 1998. Pp 123- 140.
- Yerima, Ahmed. "Hard Ground" Ibadan: Kraft Books, 2005. Print.